

Derivatives of 2,4-Dihalogeno-3,5-dinitrotoluenes

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The preparation and characterisation of 2,4-dichloro-3,5-dinitro-(I), 2-chloro-4-bromo-3,5-dinitro-(II), and 2-chloro-4-iodo-3,5-dinitro-(III) toluenes and of products obtained from them by reaction with ammonia, methylamine, dimethylamine, aniline, and *m*- and *p*-toluidines have been described.

Compounds (I) and (II) have been obtained by dinitration¹ of 2,4-dichloro- and 2-chloro-4-bromo-toluene respectively, whereas (III) has been obtained by replacement of the amino group in 3-chloro-2,6-dinitro-4-methylaniline² by iodine. The latter has been obtained by dinitration of 3-chloro-6-nitro-4-methylaniline³.

Both the halogen atoms in 2,4-dihalogeno-3,5-dinitrotoluenes are likely to be reactive as these have two nitro groups either in both the *ortho* or in the *ortho* and *para* positions. Both of them, however, are not replaced when heated with different reagents. In all the derivatives prepared, chlorine is invariably present and the derivatives of all the three dihalogeno-dinitrotoluenes with a nucleophilic reagent are identical, indicating that in these reactions only the halogen at position 4 is substituted.

This preferential replacement of the halogen atom cannot be due to steric hindrance because in 1,2,4-trihalogeno-3,5-dinitrobenzenes, both the reactive halogens, which are similarly placed as in compounds (I-III), are replaced by nucleophilic groups.

The spatial consideration reveals that NO₂ group at position 3 in 2,4-dihalogeno-3,5-dinitrotoluenes is effectively held out of the plane of the ring by the bulky halogen atoms. Moreover, the 'H' atoms of methyl group are tetrahedrally placed. Therefore, the approach of the nucleophilic reagent at position 2 via any mode SN₁ or SN₂ is inhibited due to the *non-bonded interaction* of the tetrahedrally placed 'H' atom of the methyl group on one side and the 'O' atom of the twisted nitro group on the other side. Though NO₂ group at position 3 in 1,2,4-trihalogeno-3,5-dinitrobenzenes is also effectively held out of the plane of the benzene ring by the bulky halogen atoms, the other side is free from such interactions because a halogen atom at position 1 is in the plane of the ring and therefore the nucleophilic reagent is free to attack at position 2 from this side. The spatial details of a halogen atom at position 4, both in 2,4-dihalogeno-3,5-dinitrotoluenes and 1,2,4-trihalogeno-3,5-dinitrobenzenes, are the same. This is substituted easily in both the cases. That this type of non-bonded interaction is responsible for the inhibition of replacement of a halogen atom at position 2 in 2,4-dihalogeno-3,5-dinitrotoluenes is corroborated by the fact that neither 2,4-dihalogeno-3,5-dinitrotoluenes nor 1,2,4-trihalogeno-3,5-dinitrobenzenes react with *o*-toluidine.

1. Cohen and Smithals, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 105, 1909.

2. Davies, *ibid.*, 1921, 119, 876.

3. Cohen and Dakin, *ibid.*, 1902, 81, 1348.

EXPERIMENTAL

3-Chloro-2,6-dinitro-4-methylaniline.—To a solution of 3-chloro-6-nitro-4-methylaniline (6 g.) in H_2SO_4 (40 ml, d 1.8), cooled to 0° , fuming nitric acid (6 ml, d 1.5) was added dropwise with vigorous shaking. The mixture was allowed to attain the room temperature and then poured on crushed ice. The crude 3-chloro-2,6-dinitro-4-methylaniline, originally precipitated as a gummy mass, soon solidified. It was filtered, washed well with water, and crystallised from glacial acetic acid as yellow crystals, m.p. 137° , corresponding to that previously reported².

2-Chloro-4-iodo-3,5-dinitrotoluenes.—(a) 3-Chloro-2,6-dinitro-4-methylaniline (2 g.), dissolved in sulphuric acid monohydrate (20 ml), was diazotised at 0° with sodium nitrite (1.6 g.). After $\frac{1}{2}$ hour the mixture was treated with a solution of potassium iodide (20 g.) in minimum amount of water. The 2-chloro-4-iodo-3,5-dinitrotoluene was isolated in the usual manner and crystallised from ethanol in yellow flakes (1.5 g.), m.p. 122° . (Found: N, 7.98. $C_7H_4O_4N_4ClI$ requires N, 8.17%.)

(b). To a suspension of 2-chloro-4-iodotoluene (5 g.) in H_2SO_4 (40 ml, d 1.8) fuming nitric acid (2.5 ml, d 1.5) was added dropwise with vigorous shaking. When all the nitric acid had been added, the mixture was heated on a water bath for 6 hours. It was cooled and poured on ice. The nitrated product separating was crystallised from ethanol in yellow flakes, m.p. 122° , undepressed on admixture with the sample obtained under (a).

2,4-Dichloro- and 2-Chloro-4-bromo-3,5-dinitro-toluenes.—Employing the procedure as described under (b), dinitration¹ of 2,4-dichlorotoluene afforded 2,4-dichloro-3,5-dinitrotoluene, m.p. 104° and that of 2-chloro-4-bromotoluene yielded 2-chloro-4-bromo-3,5-dinitrotoluene, m.p. 110° .

Reactions with Nucleophilic Reagents.—A mixture of a dihalogeno-dinitrotoluene (0.01 M) and aniline, *m*-toluidine, or *p*-toluidine (as the case may be) (0.01 M), sodium acetate (2 g.), and ethanol (10 ml) was refluxed for 2 hours. A yellow or orange compound separating was crystallised from ethanol.

TABLE I
Derivatives of 2-chloro-4-halogeno-3,5-dinitrotoluenes.

Reagent.	Derivatives.	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	%Chlorine.	
					Found.	Reqd.
Aniline	$R = H; R_1 = Ph$	190°	Orange	$C_{15}H_{10}O_4N_5Cl$	11.71	11.54
<i>m</i> -Toluidine	$R = H; R_1 = m\text{-Tol}$	110°	Deep yellow	$C_{14}H_{12}O_4N_5Cl$	11.11	11.04
<i>p</i> -Toluidine	$R = H; R_1 = p\text{-Tol}$	187°	Orange-yellow	$C_{14}H_{10}O_4N_5Cl$	10.90	11.04
Ammonia	$R = R_1 = H^a$	137°	Yellow	..	..	..
Methylamine	$R = H; R_1 = Me$	160°	Orange	$C_9H_9O_4N_5Cl$	14.32	14.48
Dimethylamine	$R = R_1 = Me$	136°	Deep yellow	$C_9H_{10}O_4N_5Cl$	13.56	13.68

A saturated ethanolic solution (10 ml) of ammonia, methylamine, or dimethylamine was mixed with a dihalogeno-dinitrotoluene (1 g.) and the whole was refluxed for 2 hours. The products were isolated in the usual way and crystallised from ethanol.

Identical derivatives were obtained from 2,4-dichloro-, 2-chloro-4-bromo-, and 2-chloro-4-iodo-3,5-dinitrotoluenes. Identity of the products was established by determining mixed m.p. and comparing their analytical results. Derivatives of these and their characteristics are recorded in Table I.

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